

E-ISSN: 3043-601X

VOLUME 2; ISSUE 1 - APRIL, 2026

RESISTANCE AND MOLECULAR DETECTION OF VIRULENCE-ASSOCIATED GENES OF *AEROMONAS HYDROPHILA* ISOLATED FROM RAW ORGANS OF CHICKEN (*GALLUS GALLUS DOMESTICUS*) AND AFRICAN CATFISH (*CLARIAS GARIEPINUS*) IN ENUGU

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doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19829696

ABSTRACT

Aeromonas hydrophila is an opportunistic, Gram-negative bacterium widely distributed in aquatic environments and known to cause significant infections in both human and animals. In aquaculture and poultry systems, *A. hydrophila* is a key pathogen contributing to severe economic losses due to its pathogenicity, zoonotic potential and increasing antimicrobial resistance. The emergence of virulent and multidrug-resistant *A. hydrophila* strains in food sources such as chicken and fish pose a serious public health concern, particularly in resource-limited regions with inadequate surveillance and antimicrobial stewardship. This study aimed to isolate, characterize and determine the antimicrobial resistant genes of *A. hydrophila* obtained from raw organs of chicken (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) and African cat fish (*Clarias gariepinus*). Additionally, the work sought to detect and molecularly characterize key virulence-associated genes. It was a cross-sectional laboratory-based descriptive and

analytical study designed to isolate *A. hydrophila* from raw organs of African catfish and chicken, to determine their antimicrobial resistance pattern, and also detect selected virulence-associated genes using molecular techniques. The data were subjected to statistically analysis and significant level taken at $p \leq 0.05$. A total of three hundred samples of chicken and catfish organs (liver, intestine, gills and kidney) were aseptically collected from the animals in the laboratory. Isolation and identification were performed using culture media and biochemical tests, while molecular genotyping was done using polymerase chain reaction (PCR) to detect specific virulence genes. The in-vitro susceptibility testing involves Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) test was conducted to determine the antibiogram of the isolates. Prevalence rate of 3.7% was obtained from *A. hydrophila* while 25.3%, 16.3% and 16.0% were obtained from *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* respectively. The distribution of the isolates from different raw organs of fish and chicken was statistically significant $p = 0.013$. Antibiotic susceptibility profiling revealed a high rate of resistance to ampicillin (β -lactam), moderate susceptibility was observed for ofloxacin, ciprofloxacin, and nalidixic acid (quinolones), and gentamycin (aminoglycosides). However, amikacin (aminoglycoside) showed 100% sensitivity to the virulence positive strains and mixed reaction (50% sensitivity and 50% resistance) to the virulence negative strains of the *A. hydrophila*. The Multiple Antibiotic Resistance (MAR) index ranged between 0.17-0.75. Molecular analysis showed that aerolysin (*aerA*), cytotoxic enterotoxin (*act*) and heat-labile cytotoxic enterotoxins (*alt*), were the virulent genes detected at 18.2% and 9.1% in chicken and fish respectively. The detection of multiple virulent genes alongside antimicrobial resistance highlights the potential health risks associated with the consumption or handling of contaminated poultry and fish products. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of continuous surveillance of food borne pathogens and the need for improved hygienic practices during slaughtering, processing, and distribution of animal derived foods.

KEYWORDS: *Aeromonas hydrophila*, Virulence, Resistance, Chicken, African catfish

INTRODUCTION

Aeromonas hydrophila is a gram-negative bacterium commonly found in aquatic environments and known to infect a wide range of hosts including fish, poultry and humans (Jeamsripong *et al.*, 2025). It is an emerging zoonotic pathogen associated with foodborne illnesses and various infections in both humans and animals. Kelany *et al.*, (2024) opined that of growing concern is its ability to harbor virulence genes and exhibit multidrug resistance, making it a significant public health threat. The first isolates of *Aeromonas* was reported by Sanarelli, (1891), who named the bacteria; *Bacillus hydrophilus fuscus* (now *Aeromonas hydrophila*). However, the International Committee of Systemic Bacteriology established the authorship of the genus to Stanier in 1943 (Stanier, 1943). Traditionally, Farmer *et al.*, (2006) reported that the genera *Aeromonas* and *Plesiomonas* have been considered together but they are two different genus.

The genus *Aeromonas* comprises of more than 36-gram negative bacterial species (Fernandez-Bravo & Figueras, 2020; Ahmed *et al.*, 2021; Conte *et al.*, 2021). Tomas, (2012), indicated that the most common species of *Aeromonas* that cause disease in fish are: *A. hydrophila*, *A. sobria*, *A. veronii* and *A. salmonicida*; while the potential human pathogens are usually *A. hydrophila*, *A. caviae*, *A. schubertii*, *A. jandaei* and *A. sobria (veronii)* as averred by Lamy *et al.*, (2010). The species *Aeromonas hydrophila* is the most common within the genus (Santos *et al.*, 2010). It has been isolated and identified from healthy fish. *Aeromonas hydrophila* is the most virulent specie within the genus, *Aeromonas* (Cyrino *et al.*, 2004).

Genus *Aeromonas* comprises of motile bacilli or coccobacilli rods, that are non-spore-forming with rounded ends that are 1 -3.5 micrometer across. It belongs to the class of Gamma-proteobacteria and the family *Aeromonadaceae* (Janda & Abbott, 2010). The members of this genus are characterized as Gram negative bacilli (0.3 – 1.0 X 1.0 – 3.5 μm) and motile by a single polar flagellum (Horneman *et al.*, 2007). The organism is positive for oxidase, indole

and catalase, and capable of converting nitrates to nitrites, and they are glucose fermenters (Martinez-Murcia *et al.*, 2016).

Aeromonas species are typically fresh water bacteria, being found in many environments, including soil and water; ground water, drinking water at treatment plants, distribution systems and reservoirs; and in clean and polluted lakes and rivers (Horneman *et al.*, 2007). The bacteria are found in about 1% - 27 % of drinking water (Public Health Agency of Canada, 2011).

Yu *et al.*, (2004) observed that the pathogenesis of *A. hydrophila* is multifactorial but the disease mechanisms have not been clearly elucidated. The bacteria is an opportunistic pathogen because of its association with both dysenteric diarrheal and extra-intestinal infections in persons with impaired immune system (Opara & Nnodim, 2014). While Oiseth, *et al.*, (2024) reported that it is also associated with cellulitis, Minnaganti *et al.*, (2000) indicated that it is associated with necrotizing fasciitis and (Janda & Abbot, 2010) opined its link with myonecrosis & eczema in people with compromised immune systems.

Aeromonas hydrophila genomes are encoding different types of virulence factors such as: aerolysin (**aer**), cytotoxic enterotoxin (**act**), heat-stable hemolysin (**hly**) and heat-stable cytotoxic enterotoxin (**ast**) (Rasmussen-Ivey *et al.*, 2016; Samayanpaulraj *et al.*, 2020; Sherif *et al.*, 2023). These are the most studied virulence determinants in *A. hydrophila*, however, there are others which might also play a role in its pathogenicity, such as lipase, elastase, flagella, capsules, type III secretion, outer membrane proteins and DNases (Rasmussen-Ivey *et al.*, 2016; Yassen *et al.*, 2021; Sherif *et al.*, 2023). Vilches *et al.*, (2004) reported that the bacteria virulence factors are related to the invasion, replication and evasion of the host immune system, causing injuries during pathogenesis of the disease. Physical factors influence the microbial growth rate, such as temperature and pH values. However, little is known about how these factors can modify the expression of the virulence genes in the pathogenic microbes.

Praveen *et al.*, (2014), reported that *Aeromonas* species have been found as emerging pathogen, having highly specific mechanisms for promoting diseases. According to Schuetz, 2019, the classification of *Aeromonas* as true enteropathogen has been under discussion for a long time (Schuetz, 2019). Aeromonads are considered emergent pathogen and its detection in various diarrheal stool samples clearly shows they are not far from clinical routine as other enteric microorganisms as indicated by Liu *et al.*, (2025); Mohan *et al.*, (2017); and Mbuthia *et al.*, (2018). Several case reports like Parker & Shaw, (2011); Ahmed *et al.*, (2021); Meng *et al.*, (2021) reported that Aeromonads infection have demonstrated the wide range of clinical manifestations, these organisms can produce in human host. Most reports classify *Aeromonas*'s human infections as events caused by "rare" or uncommon" microorganism (Lai *et al.*, 2007; Khalil *et al.*, 2013; Hasan *et al.*, 2018; Salehi *et al.*, 2019).

Thus Niel *et al.*, (2024) reported that systemic form of infection is often fatal, particularly in patients with underlying chronic diseases, while recent trends demonstrate rising numbers of hospital-acquired *Aeromonas* infections, especially in immune-compromised individuals. As such, Parveen *et al.*, (2016) indicated that *Aeromonas* species should be continuously monitored in food products as they are a source of food borne infection. Infection is spread via fecal-oral transmission during direct ingestion or drinking of contaminated water or food (Horneman *et al.*, 2007). The organism has been readily isolated from a wide variety of foods such as fish, eggs, vegetables, sea food, raw milk, raw meat, raw vegetables and water contaminated with *A. hydrophila*. It is widely prevalent in diverse aquatic environment and has the potential to infect amphibians, fish, and mammals (Tomas, 2012). Kirov *et al.*, (2012) recorded that 50% of the raw milk samples were contaminated by *Aeromonas hydrophila*. A large epidemic of *A. hydrophila* was described in college from China by Zhang (2012). In a

research conducted in India, 11.7% of the food tested has seven different *Aeromonas* species. The highest percentages of the isolates were chicken 28.6%, followed by fish 20% and sprout 2.5% of samples as reported by Nagar, (2011).

In poultry, *Aeromonas* is less commonly documented but it is increasingly recognized, especially through contaminated feed sources such as fish meal (Fatma & Mohammed, 2012). In aquaculture, *A. hydrophila* is a frequent cause of fish disease outbreaks leading to significant economic losses. There are several species of aeromonads such as *Aeromonas hydrophila* that can infect fish and other aquatic animals and spread diseases to them as reported by Abdella *et al.*, (2017); and Fernandez-Bravo & Figueras, (2020). Besides being a fish pathogen, it also cause diseases for humans and can be ubiquitous in aquatic environments, foods, and food processing and storage facilities (Stratev *et al.*, 2021). *Aeromonas* species are well-known fish pathogens, several of which have been recognized as emerging human pathogens. The organism is capable of causing a wide spectrum of diseases in humans, ranging from gastroenteritis, wound infections and septicemia to devastating necrotizing fasciitis. In fish, *Aeromonas* species causes hemorrhagic septicemia, ulcer disease and Motile *Aeromonas* septicemia (MAS) (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Zhao *et al.*, 2019). These diseases can result in high mortality rates and high economic losses in aquaculture (Elseshhtawy *et al.*, 2019).

In livestock production particularly poultry and aquaculture, the misuse and overuse of antibiotics have contributed to the emergence of resistant bacteria strains. This has led to increased attention toward *A. hydrophila* not only as a pathogen but as a reservoir of antimicrobial resistance genes. Detecting and understanding the resistance mechanisms and virulence factors in *A. hydrophila* is crucial for developing strategies to ensure food safety and prevent the spread of antimicrobial resistance (Mousa & El-Sayed 2023).

Among different control measures that can be applied in the fish farms are antibiotics, vaccines, probiotics, and application of biosecurity measures (Assefa & Abunna, 2018). However, the emergent of antibiotics resistance and the diversity of *Aeromonas* strains pose challenges for the effective control of these diseases as reported by Sherif & Kassab, (2023). Resistance to tetracycline antibiotics such as oxytetracycline and doxycycline, is commonly observed in *A. hydrophila* isolates from aquaculture context. These antibiotics are extensively being used in fish farming for disease prevention and treatment (Goudarztalejerdi *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, *A. hydrophila* has shown an increasing resistance trend to fluoroquinolones like ciprofloxacin and enrofloxacin. Furthermore, resistance to sulfonamides and trimethoprim, often administered together, has been documented in *A. hydrophila* strains isolated from aquaculture (Thaotumpitak *et al.*, 2023). Certain *A. hydrophila* isolates also demonstrate resistance to beta-lactam antibiotics like ampicillin and cephalosporins, widely utilized in human and veterinary medicine (Saengsitthisak *et al.*, 2020; Abdella *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, some strains of *Aeromonas hydrophila* exhibits resistance to macrolide antibiotics, including erythromycin and azithromycin (Saengsitthisak *et al.*, 2020).

There is very limited published work on *A. hydrophila* isolated from raw organs of chicken (liver, kidney intestine) sold in local markets. Previous studies in Nigeria have examined either poultry or fish but none have simultaneously compared both animal sources within Enugu metropolis. There has limited research linking virulence gene profile to AMR pattern, this study will therefore bridge this gap by correlating antimicrobial resistance with virulence genes.

Hence, the study was aimed at investigating antimicrobial resistance in *Aeromonas hydrophila*, and to detect specific virulence genes from raw organs of chicken and fish in Enugu, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- **Study Area**

The study was carried out in Enugu, Enugu State, which is located within the South East geographical region of Nigeria. The state shares border with Abia state (to the south), Ebonyi state (to the east), Imo state (towards the southwest), Anambra (towards the west), Kogi (towards the northeast) and Benue state (to the north). It is located at -90 to 90 latitude and -180 to 180 for longitude. It has an average temperature is 21 to 34 °C. It is humid and located in a tropical savanna climate with an average annual rainfall of about 2000mm.

- **Sample Size**

Three hundred samples comprising of 150 chicken and 150 fish (intestine, liver, kidney, and gill) were collected from animals selected from different locations in Enugu metropolis.

Table 1: Location of the collected catfish and chickens

Zone	Location	Local Government
Zone 1	Ogui	Enugu North
Zone 2	Abakpa	Enugu East
Zone 3	Gariki	Enugu South

- **Ethical Consideration**

The Health Research Ethics Committee of Enugu state Ministry of Health reviewed and approved the study protocol.

- **Sample Size Determination**

The sample size for the study was determined using the equation described by Charan & Biswas, (2013).

$$n = \frac{Z^2 * P [1 - P]}{E^2}$$

Where;

n = Minimum sample size required

Z = Z-score corresponding to 95% confidence level (1.96)

P = Prevalence of 19.6% in fish samples (Adah *et al.*, 2020)

E = Margin of error tolerated (0.05)

Hence

$$n = \frac{[1.96]^2 \times 0.196 (1 - 0.196)}{[0.05]^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.196 \times 0.84}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 242$$

Hence, the minimum sample size was 242 specimen.

An attrition rate of 20% was anticipated,

$$= 20\% \text{ of } 242$$

$$= \frac{20 \times 242}{100}$$

$$= 48.4$$

$$= 48.4 + 242 = 290.4$$

- **Collection of Samples**

A total of 150 fish and 150 chicken organs were collected aseptically in sterile containers in the laboratory and were analyzed immediately.

Isolation, phenotypic, morphology and biochemical characterization of *A. hydrophila*

The collected fish and chicken organs were disinfected by rinsing with clean water and sodium hypochloride. (Collymore *et al.*, 2014). The internal organs of the fish and chicken (intestine, liver, gills and kidney) were subjected to bacteriological examination. Two grams of each sample were aseptically weighed and homogenized in 18ml of sterile buffered peptone water using a stomacher for 1-2 minutes to obtain a uniform 1:10 dilution. The homogenates were used for subsequent bacterial isolation and inoculated onto a solid media (brilliant green bile agar media), incubated at 37 °C for 18 -24 hours by plate streaking method. Colony from freshly obtained bacterial culture was sub-cultured to obtain a pure culture of *A. hydrophila*. Pure cultures of *A. hydrophila* was subjected to Gram staining and viewed microscopically. Colony morphology, culture and microscopic characteristic were observed according to the protocol recommended by Muratori *et al.*, (2001) and Xiao *et al.*, (2008). The isolates of *A. hydrophila* were characterized by biochemical tests like indole test, catalase test, and oxidase tests as for identification as previously performed by Fang *et al.* (2006). Other isolated organisms were also identified with tests like: coagulase tube test, urease test, hemolysis reaction, motility test and cold incubation test.

- **Susceptibility Testing**

The antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) of all the isolates of *A. hydrophila* was done using disk diffusion method as described by Kirby-Bauer test following Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guideline on Mueller- Hinton agar. A loop full of bacteria was taken from a pure culture colony and transferred to a tube containing 5mls of normal saline and mixed gently until it forms a homogenous suspension. The turbidity of the suspension was adjusted to the turbidity of 0.5 McFarland in order to standardize the inoculum size. A sterile cotton swab was dipped, rotated across the wall of the tube to avoid excess fluid, and was evenly inoculated on Muller-Hinton Agar, then seeded with antibiotics disc. This was performed using different classes of antibiotics such as cephalosporins (ceftriaxone and cefotaxime 30µg), quinolones (ofloxacin 5µg, ciprofloxacin 5µg, nalixidic acid 30µg), macrolides (erythromycin 15µg), beta lactam (ampicillin 10µg), and aminoglycoside

(gentamycin 10 μ g, amikacin 30 μ g, streptomycin 10 μ g), at different concentration of the drugs, incubated at 37⁰ C for 24 hours. The AST result interpretation was based on the CLSI criteria as sensitive, intermediate and resistance (CLSI, 2020).

- **Molecular Detection of Virulent Gene Using PCR**

Kit used for DNA Extraction

Materials: Quick-DNATM Miniprep plus kit (Zymo Research), centrifuge (EPPENDORF, Germany), vortex mixer, block heater (WEALTEC CORP, Taiwan), microwave oven (SCANFROST China), pipettes, digital scales, microcentrifuge tubes, gel tank, gel comb, scientific power pack (CLEAVER SCIENTIFIC, Taiwan), gel documentation system (VILBER, Germany).

Genomic DNA extracted using quick-DNATM Miniprep plus kit (Zymo research), according to recommended protocol.

PCR Protocol

Two hundred microliters (200 μ l) of each sample was added to a micro-centrifuge tube, 200 μ l of BioFluid and cell buffer and 20 μ l of proteinase K was added to it and mixed thoroughly using a vortex for 10- 15 seconds and then incubated the tube at 55⁰C for 10 minutes on a heating block. One volume genomic binding buffer (420 μ l) was added to the digested sample and mixed thoroughly with a vortex mixer for 10 -15 seconds. The mixture was then transferred to a Zymo-SpinTM 11C-XL column in a collection tube and centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 1 minute. The collection tube was discarded with the flow through. Four hundred microliters (400 μ l) DNA pre-wash buffer was added to the spin column in a new collection tube and centrifuged at 12,000 X g for 1 minute. The collection tube was emptied and 700 μ l g- DNA wash buffer was added to the spin column and centrifuged at \geq 12,000 x g for 1 minute. The spin column was then transferred to a clean micro-centrifuge tube. 50 μ l of DNA elution buffer was added directly on the matrix and incubated for 5 minutes at room temperature, then centrifuged at maximum speed for 1 minute to elute the DNA. The eluted DNA was stored at \leq 20⁰ C for future use.

- **AERA Gene Amplification**

The amplification for the *aerA* gene was done using the following protocol:

12.5 μ l of one taq quick load 2X master mix with standard buffer (New England Biolabs Inc); 0.5 μ l each of forward and reverse primers (AERA F; CAAGAACA AGTTCAAGGACG and AERA R; GGTAGTGGTTGAAGTGGAAG); 6.5 μ l of nuclease free water and 5 μ l of DNA template was used to prepare 25 μ l reaction volume of the PCR cocktail.

The reaction was gently mixed and transferred to themalcycler. Amplification conditions for the PCR was as follows: initial denaturation for 5 minutes at 94⁰ C for 30 seconds, primer annealing at 48.5⁰ C for 30 seconds and strand extension at 72⁰ C for 5 minutes on an Eppendorf nexus gradient mastercycler (Germany). PCR products were separated on a 1.5% agarose gel and DNA bands were visualized with ethidium bromside.

ACT Amplification

The amplification for the *act* gene was done using the following protocol, 12.5 μ l of one Taq quick-load 2X master mix with standard buffer (new England Biolabs Inc); 0.5 μ l each of forward and reverse primers (ACT F; ATGGAAGTCAAGGAAACCAC and ACT R;

TTGCCATTTCCAGCCTTC); 6.5 μ l of nuclease free water and 5 μ l of DNA template was used to prepare 25 μ l reaction volume of the PCR cocktail.

The reaction was gently mixed and transferred to thermalcycler. Amplification condition for the PCR was as follows: initial denaturation for 5 minutes at 94⁰C, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation at 94⁰C for 30 seconds, primer annealing at 52⁰C for 30 seconds and strands extension at 72⁰ C for 30 seconds. Final extension at 72⁰C for 5 minutes on an Eppendorf, nexus gradient mastercycle (Germany).

PCR products were separated on a 1.5% agarose DNA gel and DNA bands were visualize with ethidium bromide.

ALT Amplification

The amplification for the *alt* gene was done using the following protocol: 12.5 μ l of one Taq Quick- load 2X Master mix with standard buffer (New England Bio labs Inc); each of forward and reverse primers (ALT F; GTGAAAGGACCTGCGAGCG and ALT R; TTGGCACGGGTTGTTATTCC) 6.5 μ l of nuclease free water and 5 μ l of DNA templates was used to prepare 25 μ l reaction volume of the cocktail. The reaction was gently mixed and transferred to the thermalcycler.

Amplification conditions for the PCR was as follows: initial denaturation for 5 minutes at 94⁰C, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation at 94⁰C for 30 seconds, primer annealing at 52⁰C for 30 seconds and stand extension at 72⁰ C for 30 seconds. Final extension for 72⁰ C for 5 minutes on an Eppendorf nexus gradient Mastercycler (Germany).

PCR products were separated on a 1.5% agarose gel and DNA bands were visualized with Ethidium bromide.

Agarose Gel Electrophoresis

Agarose gel (1.5%) was prepared by dissolving 1.5g of agarose in 100ml of 1X TBE Buffer. The mixture was heated to a clear solution using a microwave oven and allowed to cool to about 50⁰ C. 5 μ l of Ethidium bromide was added into the solution and mixed thoroughly. The agarose preparation was carefully poured into a gel tray, with the gel comb in place and was allowed to solidify. The tray was loaded into the gel tank and 1X TBE buffer was poured into the tank, making sure that the gel was properly submerged. The gel comb was carefully removed. 5 μ l of amplicon was loaded into the wells. The tank was connected to the power and set to run at 120 volts for 40 minutes after which it was viewed on a gel documentation system

Table 2: Oligonucleotide primers used in the study:

Target gene	primers sequence	Annealing Temperature	Amplicon size (bp)
AERA	5 ¹ : CAAGAACAAGTTCAAGGAGG 3 ¹ 5 ¹ : GGTAGTGGTTGAAGTGGAAG 3 ¹	48.3 ⁰ C	390 – 500
ACT	5 ¹ : ATGGAAGTCAAGGAAACCAC 3 ¹ 5 ¹ : TTGCCATTTCCAGCCTTC 3 ¹	52 ⁰ C	1100-1240
ALT	5 ¹ : GTGAAAGGACCTGCGAGCG 3 ¹ 5 ¹ : TTGGCACGGGTTGTTATTCC 3 ¹	52 ⁰ C	442 – 670

Key: AERA (aerA) = Aerolysin; ACT (actin) = Acetyltransferases; ALT (alt) = Aeromonas heat-liable cytotoxic enterotoxin.

- **Statistical Analysis:**

All data were statistically analyzed using the Microsoft excel IBM Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 27. Data of the isolated *Aeromonas hydrophila* were expressed using simple percentage and the prevalence of the different variables were compared using the chi-square. P-values <0.05 (level of significant) were considered as significant.

RESULT

- **General characteristics of the Samples Collected**

A total of 300 raw organs of fish and chicken (specimen) were collected for the study, comprising of 150 chicken and 150 fish specimens. The specimens were collected from different parts of the animal like gill, intestine, kidney and liver of the raw organs of fish and chicken. The animals were drawn from different market in Enugu zone: Abakpa market representing Enugu east, Old Artisan market representing Enugu north and Gariki and Kenyetta market representing Enugu south. Majority of the specimen were intestine (58.7%) (Table 3).

Table 3: Population of Samples collected

Sample	Fish (n)	Chicken (n)	Percent (%)
Gills	12	0	4.0
Intestine	52	124	58.7
Kidney	19	16	11.7
Liver	67	10	25.6
Total	150	150	100

Biochemical Reaction of Isolated Organisms

Table 4 shows the biochemical reactions used to identify the isolated organisms; catalase test, coagulase test, indole test, motility testing, citrate utilization test, urease test and hemolysis reaction. Gram staining was also conducted to differentiate the isolates into Gram positive and Gram-negative organisms.

Table 4: Biochemical Tests for the Identification of the Isolated Bacteria

Organism	Gram Stain	Coagulase	Oxidase	Indole	Motility	Catalase	Hemolysis	Citrate	Urea	Others
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	- Rod	-	+	+	+	+	β -hemolytic	+	-	Ferments glucose
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	+ Rod	-	+	-	+	+	β -hemolytic	+	-	Esculin (+)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	- Rod	-	-	+	+	+	β -hemolytic	-	-	Methyl Red (+)
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	- Rod	-	-	-	+	+	γ -hemolytic	+	-	Voges-Proskauer (+)
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	+ Cocci	-	-	-	-	+	γ -hemolytic	-	-	Bile-esculin (+), Growth in 6.5% NaCl (+), PYR (+)
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	+ Cocci	-	-	-	Tumbling motility	+	β -hemolytic	-	-	Cold growth at 4°C (+), CAMP test (+)
<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	+ Cocci	-	+	-	+	+	β -hemolytic	+	-	
<i>Propionibacterium avidum</i>	+ Rod	-	-	-	-	+	γ -hemolytic	-	+	
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	- Rod	-	+	-	+	+	β -hemolytic	+	-	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+ Cocci	+	-	-	-	+	β -hemolytic	+	+	Mannitol fermentation (+), DNase (+)

- **Distribution of the isolates from raw organs**

Table 5 showed a prevalence rate of 3.7% (11/300) of *Aeromonas hydrophila* isolated from raw organs of fish and chicken. Other gram negative organisms isolated include: *Enterobacter cloacae* (25.3%), *E. coli* (16.3%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (11%) while some of the gram positive organisms include *Staphylococcus aureus* (16%), *Listeria monocytogenes*, (0.3%), *Micrococcus luteus* and *Enterococcus faecalis* (7.3%).

Table 5: Distribution of the isolated micro-organisms from raw organs based on gram reaction:

Organism	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gram negative		
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	11	3.7
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	49	16.3
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	76	25.3
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	33	11.0
Total	169	56.3
Gram positive		
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	22	7.3
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	1	0.3
<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	23	7.7
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	48	16.0
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	22	7.3
<i>Propionbacteria avidum</i>	15	5.0
Total	131	43.7

- **The distribution of bacterial species from chicken and fish organs**

Table 6 showed the distribution of bacteria species from chicken and fish organs. *A. hydrophila* isolated was more in the fish 2.7% (8/300) than in chicken 1.0% (3/100). The Chi-square test revealed statistically significant difference in the distribution of bacterial isolates of chicken and fish specimen ($X^2 = 20.925$, $df = 9$, $p = 0.013$).

Table 6: Distribution of the Isolates from different specimens:

Isolates	Chicken	Fish	Total	p-value	chi-square	df
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	3 (1.0)	8 (2.7)	11	0.013	20.595	9
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	15 (5.0)	7 (2.3)	22			
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	34 (11.3)	15(5.0)	49			
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	33 (11.0)	43(14.3)	76			
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	10 (3.3)	12 (4.0)	22			
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	1			
<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	10(3.3)	13 (4.3)	23			
<i>Propionibacteria avidum</i>	8 (2.7)	7 (7.3)	15			
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	10 (3.3)	23 (7.7)	23			
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	26 (8.7)	22 (7.3)	48			
Total	150 (50)	150 (50)	300			

- **Distribution of the Isolates based on the part of the organ:**

Table 7 showed the distribution of the isolated organisms based on the organ. Highest organism isolated were *Enterobacter cloacae* (18.3%), followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* (11.3%) which were all isolated from the intestine of raw organs of chicken and fish. However *A. hydrophila*, recorded 3 (1.0%) in the kidney, 7 (2.3%) in the intestine and 1 (0.3%) in the liver. Meanwhile, no organism was isolated from the gills of fish. The result when compared with Chi-square test, showed a statistically significant association between the different parts of organs of fish and chicken, and the distribution of the bacterial isolates ($X^2 = 60.632$, $df = 36$, $p = 0.006$)

Table 7: Distribution of the isolates and the parts of the organs

Organism	Gill	Intestine	Kidney	Liver	p-value	chi square	df
<i>A. hydrophila</i>	0 (0)	7 (2.3)	3 (1.0)	1 (0.3)	0.006	60.632	36
<i>B. cereus</i>	0 (0)	16 (5.3)	2 (0.7)	4 (1.3)			
<i>E. coli</i>	2 (0.7)	29 (9.7)	8 (2.7)	10 (3.4)			
<i>E. cloacae</i>	3 (1.0)	55 (18.3)	6 (2.0)	12 (4.0)			
<i>E. faecalis</i>	1 (0.3)	19 (6.3)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)			
<i>L monocytogenes</i>	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)			
<i>M. luteus</i>	3 (1.0)	13 (4.3)	1 (0.3)	6 (2.0)			
<i>P. avidum</i>	0 (0)	7 (2.3)	2 (0.7)	6 (2.0)			
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	0 (0)	21 (7.0)	5 (1.7)	7 (2.3)			
<i>Staph. aureus</i>	3 (1.0)	34 (11.3)	3 (1.0)	8 (2.7)			
Total	12 (4)	202 (67.3)	31 (10.3)	55 (18.3)			

- **Distribution of the Isolates and the location of the organ.**

Table 8 revealed that *Enterobacter cloacae* recorded highest prevalence in Enugu east and Enugu north at 12.2% and 10.0% respectively. However, *Aeromonas hydrophila* was isolated more in Enugu north (1.7%) than in Enugu east and Enugu south (1.0%). The Chi-square test revealed a statistically significant differences in the distribution of bacterial isolates and the location where it was sourced ($X^2 = 30.415$, $df = 18$, $p = 0.034$).

Table 8: Distribution of the Isolates based on the sampling location.

Organisms	EN East	EN North	EN South	p-value	chi square	df
<i>A. hydrophila</i>	3 (1.0)	5 (1.7)	3 (1.0)	0.034	30.415	18
<i>B. cereus</i>	7 (2.3)	9 (3.0)	6 (2.0)			
<i>E. coli</i>	16 (5.3)	22 (7.3)	11 (3.7)			
<i>E. cloacae</i>	38 (12.7)	30 (10.0)	8 (2.7)			
<i>E. faecalis</i>	10 (3.3)	7 (2.3)	5 (1.7)			
<i>L monocytogenes</i>	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.3)			
<i>M. luteus</i>	9 (3.0)	6 (2.0)	8 (2.7)			
<i>P. avidum</i>	1 (1.0)	8 (2.7)	6 (2.0)			
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	16 (5.3)	13 (4.3)	4 (1.3)			
<i>Staph aureus</i>	19 (6.3)	12 (4.0)	17 (5.7)			
Total	119 (39.7)	112 (37.3)	69 (23.0)			

- **Distribution of the virulence genes in *A. hydrophila***

Table 9 showed that virulent genes were detected in 11 isolates of *A. hydrophila*. Of these 11 isolates, 27.3% (3/11) of the isolates were positive for ACT (act), 27.3% (3/11) were positive for ALT (alt) and also 27.3% (3/11) were positive for AERA (aerA) genes. The presence of virulent genes (ACT/ALT/AERA) was detected in isolates from chicken and fish organ in Enugu north and Enugu south. The parts of the organs examined were intestine, kidney and liver. Virulent genes were found in 18.2 % (2/11) intestine, 9.1% (1/11) of the kidney and none was found in the liver. In Enugu north, 9.1% (1/11) was identified in the intestine while no virulent genes was identified in liver and kidney. In Enugu south, 9.1% (1/11) virulent gene each was isolated from the intestine and kidney of both chicken and fish. A significant difference was observed in the distribution of virulence genes between isolates from chicken and fish in Enugu North (p-value 0.025).

Table 9: Distribution of the virulence genes based on the part of organ, and the location of specimen.

Variables	ACT/ALT/AERA	p-value	chi-square	df
Part of organ				
Intestine	2 (18.2)	0.804	0.437	2
Kidney	1 (9.1)			
Liver	0 (0.0)			
Location of specimen				
Enugu north	1 (9.1)	0.165	3.606	2
Enugu south	2 (18.2)			
Location of specimen				
Enugu north				
Chicken	1 (9.1)	0.025	5.000	1
Fish	0 (0.0)			
Location of specimen				
Enugu south				
Chicken	1 (9.1)	0.386	0.750	1
Fish	1 (9.1)			
Part of the organ				
Enugu north				
Intestine	1 (9.1)	0.659	0.833	2
Kidney	0 (0.0)			
Liver	0 (0.0)			
Part of the organ				
Enugu south				
Intestine	1 (9.1)	0.386	0.750	1
Kidney	1 (9.1)			
Total	3 (27.2)			

- **Antibiogram of the Isolated *Aeromonas hydrophila***

Table 10 showed the antibiotics susceptibility testing performed on *Aeromonas hydrophila* isolated from raw organs. *A. hydrophila* isolated were resistant to vancomycin and ofloxacin with 81.8% and 63.7% respectively. The lowest resistance was noted for ceftriaxone. An antibiogram analysis conducted to evaluate the antimicrobial resistance profile of *A. hydrophila* isolated from fish and chicken samples, where 11 of the isolates were tested against 12 antibiotics representing various classes including cephalosporins, quinolones, β -lactam, tetracycline, macrolide, glycopeptide and aminoglycosides. Out of 132 (11X12) possible isolates-antibiotics combination, the multi-antibiotics resistance (MAR) index was calculated, which revealed that *A. hydrophila* isolated, exhibit a high level of resistance to multiple antibiotics.

Table 10: Antibiogram of the isolated *A. hydrophila*:

Class of antibiotics	Name of antibiotics	Sensitive (S) (%)	Intermediate (I) (%)	Resistance (R) (%)	MAR Index
Cephalosporins	Ceftriaxone	7 (63.7)	1 (18.2)	2 (18.2)	0.17
	Cefotaxime	6 (54.6)	1 (9.1)	4 (36.4)	0.33
Quinolones	Ofloxacin	3 (27.3)	1 (9.1)	7 (63.7)	0.58
	Ciprofloxacin	2 (18.2)	3 (27.3)	6 (54.6)	0.50
	Nalidixic acid	4 (36.4)	3 (27.3)	4 (36.4)	0.33
Macrolide	Erythromycin	4 (36.4)	0 (0.0)	7 (63.7)	0.58
Beta lactam	Ampicillin	2 (18.2)	2 (18.2)	7 (63.7)	0.58
Glycopeptide	Vancomycin	1 (9.1)	1 (9.1)	9 (81.8)	0.75
Tetracycline	Tetracycline	4 (36.4)	1 (9.1)	6 (54.6)	0.50
Aminoglycoside	Gentamycin	2 (18.2)	2 (27.3)	6 (54.6)	0.50
	Amikacin	7 (63.7)	0 0	4 (36.4)	0.33
	Streptomycin	5 (45.5)	0 0	6 (54.6)	0.50

- **Correlation between the virulence gene and the antibiotic resistance on *A. hydrophila*.**

Table 11 revealed three isolates as virulence positive while eight isolates were virulence negative. Out of the three virulence positive isolates only amikacin (30 μ g) showed sensitive, while the other nine antibiotics used were resistant. Eight of the *A. hydrophila* isolates were virulence negative. Out of these eight isolates, three were completely resistant to erythromycin (15 μ g), gentamycin (10 μ g) and ampicillin (10 μ g), while the others showed mixed sensitivity.

This table also show that some antibiotics like; ceftriaxone (30 μ g), cefotaxime (30 μ g), ofloxacin (5 μ g), ciprofloxacin (5 μ g) and nalixidic acid (30 μ g) were sensitive the non virulence *A. hydrophila* but showed complete resistant to the virulence positive *A. hydrophila*. Amikacin that

showed complete sensitivity to virulence positive *A. hydrophila* however, showed mixed sensitivity of 50 % and 50% resistance to the virulence negative *A. hydrophila* isolated.

Table 11: Correlation between virulence genes and antibiotic resistance of *A hydrophila*.

Class of Antibiotics	Type of Antibiotics	ACT/ALT/AERA		p-value	chi-square	df
		Yes (n=3)	No (n=8)			
Cephalosporin	Ceftriaxone	%	%	1.547	0.461	2
	Sensitive	0 (0)	2 (25)			
	Intermediate	0 (0)	0 (0)			
	Resistant	3 (100)	6 (75)			
	Cefotaxime			1.547	0.461	2
	Sensitive	0 (0)	4 (50)			
Intermediate	0 (0)	1 (12.5)				
Resistant	3 (100)	3 (37.5)				
Quinolones	Ofloxacin			0.413	0.521	1
	Sensitive	0 (0)	2 (25.0)			
	Intermediate	0 (0)	0 (0)			
	Resistant	3 (100)	6 (75.0)			
	Ciprofloxacin			2.357	0.125	1
	Sensitive	0 (0)	2 (25)			
	Intermediate	0 (0)	0 (0)			
	Resistant	3 (100)	6 (75)			
	Nalixidic acid			0.917	0.632	2
	Sensitive	0 (0)	2 (25)			
	Intermediate	0 (0)	1 (12.5)			
	Resistant	3 (100)	5 (62.5)			
Macrolides	Erythromycin			0.917	0.338	1
	Sensitive	0 (0)	0 (0)			
	Intermediate	0 (0)	0 (0)			
Resistant	3 (100)	8(100)				
Beta lactam	Ampicillin			0.917	0.338	1
	Sensitive	0 (0)	0 (0)			
	Intermediate	0 (0)	0 (0)			
Resistant	3 (100)	8 (100)				
Glycosides	Vancomycin			0.413	0.521	1
	Sensitive	0 (0)	1 (12.5)			
Intermediate	0 (0)	1 (12.5)				

	Resistant	3 (100)	6 (75)			
Aminoglycosides	Gentamycin					
	Sensitive	0 (0)	0 (0.0)			
	Intermediate	0 (0)	0 (0.0)	0.917	0.338	1
	Resistant	3 (100)	8 (100)			
	Amikacin					
	Sensitive	3 (100)	4 (50)			
	Intermediate	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0.461	1.547	2
	Resistant	0 (0.0)	4 (50)			

Figure 1: Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR amplified ALT Gene of *A. hydrophila*

Figure 2: Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR amplified ACT Gene of *A. hydrophila*

Figure 3: Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR amplified AERA Gene of *A. hydrophila*

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the occurrence of antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes in *Aeromonas hydrophila* isolated from raw internal organs of African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) and chicken (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) obtained from selected locations in Enugu North, Enugu South and Enugu East Local Government Areas of Enugu State, Nigeria. The findings demonstrate the presence of potentially pathogenic *A. hydrophila* strains harboring antimicrobial resistance and virulence determinants in food animals intended for human consumption. Similar observations

have been reported in previous studies which identified food animals as important reservoirs of resistant and virulent *Aeromonas* species (Janda & Abbott, 2010; Pessoa *et al.*, 2019).

Food of animal origin such as meat and fish are very important sources of nutrients needed for growth, repair and maintenance of the body. Meat is rich in iron, zinc and vitamin B12 while fish is rich in omega-3 fatty acids, iodine, vitamin D and selenium. Both provide high-quality protein and are key to a balanced diet (USAD, 2020; WHO, 2020). Food (fish and chicken) as animal-based foods, harbor bacteria especially if they are not properly handled, stored or cooked. Chicken is one of the most common carriers of pathogenic bacteria while fish especially from fresh water can harbor spoilage and pathogenic bacteria. These bacteria are important cause of foodborne diseases (food poisoning) (WHO, 2020). Therefore, detection of these bacteria in food (fish/chicken) is vital particularly, *Aeromonas hydrophila* which are associated with gastrointestinal infections in humans. *Aeromonas hydrophila*, a gram-negative rod-shaped bacterium that is widely found in aquatic environment, and can be isolated from water, soil and food such as meat, ham, raw milk, offal, poultry, fish and shell fish as averred by Abdelsalam *et al.*, (2022).

In this study, the prevalence of *A. hydrophila* in fish and chicken was found to be 3.7% (11/300). This report was in line with previously report of low prevalence of *A. hydrophila* (5.7%) by Kahraman *et al.*, (2017) in Turkey. In contrast, a higher prevalence of 19.6% was reported in Kaduna State by Adah *et al* (2021); 19% by Hussain *et al.*, (2014), in India; 25% was reported by Abdel-Latef (2015) in Egypt; 58% was detected by Niamah in Iraq (2012). The differences in prevalence may be due to several factors like: regional variation, local epidemiology, study population, sample size and selection, and water quality. Other factor may include climate and seasonal changes, hygiene and sanitation practices and public health intervention (Nhin *et al.*, 2021). The prevalence of *A. hydrophila* obtained was more in fish 2.7% (8/300) when compared with chicken 1% (3/300). This differences in prevalence between fish and chicken may be attributed to several factors like: different microbiota, gut structure and function, farming practices and sampling/ detection methods (Hoel *et al.*, 2017). This isolation of *A. hydrophila* from raw internal organ of African catfish and chicken underscore the organism's ability to colonize and persist in animal tissue. Internal organs are normally sterile in healthy animals; therefore their contamination suggests systemic infection, poor slaughter hygiene, or post-mortem contamination during processing (Castro-Escarpulli *et al.*, 2003). The prevalence of *A. hydrophila* in food indicates poor hygienic practices (Basma *et al.*, 2020).

In aquaculture systems, *A. hydrophila* is a well-recognized opportunistic pathogen associated with aeromoniasis, particularly under conditions of stress, overcrowding, and poor water quality (Pessoa *et al.*, 2019). Poultry may similarly acquire *Aeromonas* species through contaminated water, feed, or farm environments (Nhung *et al.*, 2017). The implications are concerning because treatment failures in aquaculture or poultry production could accelerate pathogen dissemination and zoonotic transfer to humans through contaminated water or improperly cooked food. The recovery of *A. hydrophila* from both fish and chicken in this study suggests shared environmental reservoirs and highlights lapses in hygiene practices within Enugu metropolis.

In this study, three major virulent genes (**act**, **alt** and **aerA**) were detected in *Aeromonas hydrophila* isolates recovered from the intestines, kidneys, livers and gills of chicken and fish. The overall prevalence of these genes was higher in chicken isolates (18.2%) than in fish (9.1%) although the differences was not statistically significant ($p = 0.072$). The detection of **act** (cytotoxic enterotoxin), **alt** (heat-labile enterotoxin), and **aerA** (aerolysin) is noteworthy, as these

genes are directly associated with diarrhea diseases, tissue damage and systemic infections in both animals and humans. Our detection rates ($\leq 18.2\%$) are lower than those reported in several surveys. For example, Hoel *et al.*, (2017) found *aerA* in up to 80% of retail seafood isolates, while Abdella *et al.*, (2023) reported widespread detection of **act** and **alt** in both clinical and environmental isolates. The lower prevalence observed here may reflect regional variation, farming practices or methodological factors (Nhin *et al.*, 2021). Nonetheless, the distribution of virulence markers across organs in diseased fish and poultry, where *Aeromonas* is often systemic (Lee *et al.*, 2023).

These findings demonstrate a clear association between the antibiotic-resistant patterns of the isolates and the presence of specific virulence genes. This relationship aligns with previous research showing that antimicrobial resistance and virulence are not independent traits but often coexist due to shared genetic platforms, co-selection mechanisms, and adaptive advantages conferred under antibiotic pressure (Beceiro *et al.*, 2013). Several MDR isolates in this study, carry virulence genes commonly associated with adhesion, invasion, toxin production, or biofilm formation. This supports earlier evidence that plasmids and pathogenicity islands frequently carry both virulence and resistance genes, allowing simultaneous transmission of these traits among pathogenic bacteria (Carattoli, 2013).

Beyond virulence, isolates harboring these genes exhibited high level of resistance to commonly used antibiotics like beta lactams (ampicillin), cephalosporins, tetracycline, fluoroquinolones, and aminoglycosides (Table 11). Chen *et al.*, (2016), reported a widely documented resistance of *A. hydrophila* to commonly used antibiotics which compromised therapeutic outcome. This multi-antibiotic resistance (MAR) phenotype poses a dual public challenge by limiting therapeutic options and increasing the risk of persistence in food chain. Previous studies supported this convergence of virulence and resistance; Stratev and Odeyemi (2016) reported that foodborne *Aeromonas* isolates frequently express toxins and antibiotic resistance while Nawaz *et al.*, (2010) revealed a widespread resistance in *Aeromonas* strains recovered from fish, particularly against ampicillin and tetracycline. Several others highlighted that *A. hydrophila* stains resistant to beta-lactams, quinolones and aminoglycosides often carry virulence determinants, complicating treatment of both humans and animal infections (Mirayala & Swain, 2025; Sherif *et al.*, 2023). In Nigeria, there is an indiscriminate antibiotic use in aquaculture and poultry production because of limited regulation and easy access to antimicrobials without prescription (Okeke and Edelman, 1999). Such practices exert selective pressure that promotes the emergence and persistence of resistance strains.

The resistance genes detected in this study further confirm the genetic basis of observed resistance patterns and raise concerns about horizontal gene transfer to other pathogenic bacteria within the human gastrointestinal tract following foodborne exposure (Hossian *et al.*, 2019).

Individuals involved in aquaculture, poultry farming, slaughtering and retailing are at increased occupational risk of exposure to *A. hydrophila*. Direct contact with contaminated organs, water or surfaces may result in infection through skin abrasions or accidental ingestion (Elbashir *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, the discharge of untreated animal waste into surrounding water bodies contributes to environmental contamination and the persistence of resistant *Aeromonas* stains (Igbiosa & Okoh, 2012).

From health perspective, this result highlighted the connectedness of animals, humans and the environment. The presence of virulent, antibiotic-resistant *A. hydrophila* in food animals suggests potential zoonotic spillover, with risk of food and water borne outbreak. Moreover, the resistance trait detected may spread horizontally to other bacteria pathogens exacerbating the global antimicrobial resistance (AMR) crisis. Strengthening surveillance programs for *Aeromonas* in food production chains, coupled with judicious antibiotic use in veterinary practice, is therefore critical. Further researcher should investigate the molecular mechanism underlying resistance in *Aeromonas* as well as their potential to transfer resistance genes across bacterial population.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated the presence of key virulence genes (*act*, *alt* and *aerA*) in *A. hydrophila* isolated from chicken and fish, with high prevalence in poultry. The concurrent detection of these genes with multidrug resistance patterns underscores the dual threat posed by *A. hydrophila* as both a pathogen and a reservoir of antimicrobial resistance. These findings have important implications for food safety, public health and veterinary medicine, highlighting the need for continuous surveillance, strict regulation of antibiotic use in animal production, and the adoption of One Health approach to mitigate the risks of zoonotic transmission. Further molecular studies are warranted to elucidate resistance mechanisms and to develop effective intervention strategies for controlling the spread of virulent, drug-resistant *Aeromonas* strains.

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